

1 **Latency reversing agents.**

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6 We studied whole transcriptome dynamics by RNA-sequencing in primary human cells from HIV-1+
7 individuals in response to in vitro exposure to the latency reversing agent bryostatin. Cells displayed an
8 overt DNA damage-based primary response to bryostatin characterized by activation of *CHEK1* and
9 *RAD54L*. Cells induced the topoisomerase *TOP2A* together with PCNA clamp loading factor *PCLAF*, as
10 well as IDH3A. Proliferation was induced marked by *PCNA* induction along with activation of *CDK1*. Cells
11 responded to latency reversion by silencing *IL7R*.

12 Citations

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